

1 **Nosema ceranae (Microsporidia), a controversial 21st century honey bee pathogen**

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12 **Summary**

13 The worldwide beekeeping sector has been facing a grave threat, with losses up to 100–1000 times greater
14 than those previously reported. Despite the scale of this honey bee mortality, the causes underlying this
15 phenomenon remain unclear, yet they are thought to be multifactorial processes. *Nosema ceranae*, a
16 microsporidium recently detected in the European bee all over the world, has been implicated in the global
17 phenomenon of colony loss, although its role remains controversial. A review of the current knowledge about
18 this pathogen is presented focussing on discussion related with divergent results, trying to analyse the
19 differences specially based on different methodologies applied and divisive aspects on pathology while
20 considering a biological or veterinarian point of view. For authors, the disease produced by *N. ceranae*
21 infection cannot be considered a regional problem but rather a global one, as indicated by the wide prevalence
22 of this parasite in multiple hosts. Not only does this type of nosemosis causes a clear pathology on honeybees
23 at both the individual and colony levels, but it also has significant effects on the production of honeybee
24 products.

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36 Introduction

37 Globally, honeybees play important ecological and economic roles as pollinators of many crops and wild
38 plants (FAO, 2006; Bradbear, 2009). Current agricultural practices, such as large-scale monoculture, require a
39 seasonal abundance of honeybees in specific geographic locations that lack adequate year-round pollinator
40 populations. Managed colonies also satisfy the human demand for honeybee products such as honey, wax
41 and royal jelly (Delaplane and Mayer, 2000), especially in temperate areas of the world where most
42 professional beekeeping is practiced. Indeed, about 40% of European honeybee colonies are located in
43 temperate Mediterranean areas, such as Spain, Italy and Greece. Thus, maintaining adequate sanitary
44 conditions in honeybee colonies is crucial to ensure the continued pollination and production of honeybee
45 products.

46 For several years, the worldwide beekeeping sector has been facing a grave threat, with losses up to 100–1000
47 times greater than those previously reported (European Parliament, 2010). Despite the scale of this honey bee
48 mortality, the causes underlying this phenomenon remain unclear, yet they are thought to be multifactorial
49 processes (European Parliament, 2010; Higes *et al.*, 2010; vanEngelsdorp and Meixner, 2010). Since 2007, the
50 heightened awareness among the public and researchers has stimulated the creation of working groups and
51 increased the funding available for studies addressing this global problem, particularly in geographical areas
52 where professional beekeeping is significantly affected.

53 The microsporidium *Nosema ceranae* (1) was detected in the European honeybee at the same time in Europe
54 and Asia (Higes *et al.*, 2006; Huang *et al.*, 2007), and it is now one of the most globally prevalent honeybee
55 pathogens worldwide (Fries, 2010; Higes *et al.*, 2010; Bernal *et al.*, 2011; Traver and Fell, 2011;
56 Medici *et al.*, 2012; Martínez *et al.*, 2012). Moreover, *N. ceranae* has been implicated in the global
57 phenomenon of colony loss, although its role remains controversial. Given the direct relationship
58 between *N. ceranae* and colony losses in Spain (Higes *et al.*, 2009a; 2010), Spanish research groups have
59 actively sought to develop strategies to minimize the economic losses inflicted upon the professional sector
60 by this microsporidium. Some studies have suggested a link between this pathogen and bee colony
61 depopulation/loss in other countries with similar climatic conditions (Higes *et al.*, 2005; 2006; 2008; 2009a;
62 Bacandritsos *et al.*, 2010; Borneck *et al.*, 2010; Hatjina *et al.*, 2011; Invernizzi *et al.*, 2011; Soroker *et al.*, 2011).
63 By contrast, in countries from colder climates, the role for this microsporidium in colony loss has been ruled
64 out (Gisder *et al.*, 2010; Hedtke *et al.*, 2011; Stevanovic *et al.*, 2011; Dainat *et al.*, 2012a,b), suggesting that
65 specific conditions are required to promote these pathogenic effects of *N. ceranae*.

66 Mature spore of *Nosema ceranae* (electron microscopy).

67 Disease is the result of complex interactions between the epidemiological triad of pathogen, host and
68 environment. In farmed animals, this interaction is strongly influenced by factors related to animal husbandry
69 and management. In this review, we will discuss the factors that influence each of the components of this
70 epidemiological triad and summarize the current state of *N. ceranae* research, incorporating data from distinct
71 fields of research.

72 Can genetic variants of *Nosema ceranae* differ in their pathogenicity?

73 Several authors have proposed that the pathological effects of *N. ceranae* in Spain are associated with the
74 increased virulence of the Spanish strain (Genersch, 2010; Huang *et al.*, 2012). To confirm this hypothesis,

75 distinct genetic variants must first be accurately identified, and then they must be analysed to determine
76 whether they are associated with variation in virulence, geographic distribution or host specificity.

77 The molecular classification of microsporidia has been largely based on the analysis of ribosomal DNA (rDNA).
78 The organization of the different domains within this gene cluster varies according to species (reviewed by
79 Ironside, 2007). *Nosema ceranae* exhibits a unique rDNA unit arrangement consisting of a reversed 5S subunit
80 located at the 5' end, an intergenic spacer region (*IGS*), a small subunit (*SSU*), an internal transcribed spacer
81 (*ITS*) and a large subunit (*LSU*) at the 3' end (Huang *et al.*, 2007; 2008). While eukaryotes generally contain
82 many copies of the rDNA genes organized in tandem repeats (Eickbush and Eickbush, 2007), in *Nosema* spp.
83 this tandem conformation has only been reported for *N. apis* (Gatehouse and Malone, 1998). Multiple rDNA
84 units have been described in all chromosomes in *N. bombycis* (Liu *et al.*, 2008) and *N. ceranae*, in which 46
85 contigs containing ribosomal sequences were identified, although none contained a complete ribosomal
86 locus (Cornman *et al.*, 2009).

87 Homogeneity among the nucleotide sequences of paralogous rDNA copies is usually maintained through
88 homologous recombination and/or gene conversion between duplicated regions (Eickbush and
89 Eickbush, 2007). Accordingly, rDNA genes within a species are nearly identical, while orthologous rDNA genes
90 may differ considerably between species. However, in the case of *N. bomby*, several authors have
91 demonstrated the existence of two or more rDNA sequence variants per spore (Tay *et al.*, 2005;
92 O'Mahony *et al.*, 2007), and numerous polymorphisms have been described within single isolates
93 of *N. ceranae* (Huang *et al.*, 2008; Sagastume *et al.*, 2010).

94 These findings beg the question as to how such variability is generated. Reports of recombination
95 in *N. ceranae* (Sagastume *et al.*, 2010) are surprising in organisms believed to have an asexual mode of
96 reproduction. Thus, the only way that two sequences can recombine is if they come together in the same cell.
97 This implies the existence of a transient diploid stage after fusion, whereby different lineages in the same cell
98 undergo homologous recombination to produce a new variant that did not exist in any of the parental strains.
99 Recombination in *N. ceranae* provides better opportunities for evolution and adaptation than a strict clonal
100 mode of reproduction.

101 The existence of several non-homologous copies of a gene in a genome renders it inadequate for phylogenetic
102 purposes. Accordingly, several conflicting *Nosema* phylogenies based on *SSU* sequences have been reported
103 (Fries, 2010; Choi *et al.*, 2011). There is no consensus about the taxonomic relationships
104 between *N. ceranae* and its closest relatives: *N. apis* and *N. bomby* (Slamovits *et al.*, 2004; Vossbrinck and
105 Debrunner-Vossbrinck, 2005; Wang *et al.*, 2006; Shafer *et al.*, 2009; Chen *et al.*, 2009a; Choi *et al.*, 2011).
106 Similar results have been described for other *Nosema* species such as *N. vespula* and *N. oulemae*. While
107 some consider these species as close relatives of *N. ceranae* (Müller *et al.*, 2000; Chen *et al.*, 2009a), others
108 claim that they evolved separately from *N. vespula* (Vossbrinck and Debrunner-Vossbrinck, 2005). Similar
109 discrepancies have arisen for phylogenies based on the *LSU* (Huang *et al.*, 2007; Shafer *et al.*, 2009;
110 Choi *et al.*, 2011) and on combined data from both the *SSU* and *LSU* genes (Ironside, 2007; Shafer *et al.*, 2009).

111 Nevertheless, rDNA, and in particular its *SSU*, has been frequently used to assess the genetic diversity
112 of *N. ceranae* isolates from different geographic locations. With very few exceptions, probably biased due to
113 the analysis of very few sequences or clones (Whitaker *et al.*, 2011; Yoshiyama and Kimura, 2011), most
114 studies have demonstrated considerable variability among and/or within samples (Higes *et al.*, 2006;

115 Huang *et al.*, 2008; Chaimanee *et al.*, 2011; Suwannapong *et al.*, 2011; Medici *et al.*, 2012). Recently, a large
116 panel of cloned rDNA fragments containing the *IGS* and part of the *SSU* was analysed (Sagastume *et al.*, 2010),
117 showing that all isolates produced multiple haplotypes regardless of whether DNA was extracted from
118 individual or pooled honeybees, as described previously (Huang *et al.*, 2008). Furthermore, the haplotypes
119 obtained from a single isolate could differ by as much as those obtained from distinct isolates, with identical
120 haplotypes appearing in samples of very different origin.

121 Despite these findings, some regional clustering has been reported for Asian, North American
122 (Williams *et al.*, 2008; Chen *et al.*, 2009b) and Argentinean samples (Medici *et al.*, 2012). However, a fraction of
123 the extant haplotypes may have been overlooked since molecular cloning was not performed in these studies.
124 Indeed, direct sequencing is inappropriate to detect any geographic linkage since the sequence obtained from
125 each isolate probably represents either the most frequent genetic variant or a consensus sequence of several
126 different haplotypes.

127 The wide diversity seen in rDNA from *N. ceranae* isolates complicates the determination of taxonomic and
128 geographic relationships, and highlights the need for alternative genomic markers, ideally single copy genes
129 (Fries, 2010; Sagastume *et al.*, 2010). The draft genome assembly for *N. ceranae* (Cornman *et al.*, 2009) offers
130 a unique opportunity to obtain the necessary information, given that rDNA genotyping has proven unreliable
131 for epidemiologic and phylogenetic purposes.

132 Other *N. ceranae* loci have been recently used as alternative markers, namely those encoding polar tube
133 proteins (Chaimanee *et al.*, 2011; Hatjina *et al.*, 2011) that are thought to be highly polymorphic. Such proteins
134 are major components of the microsporidian polar filament that discharges the sporoplasm into the target cell
135 and plays an essential role in host invasion (Xu and Weiss, 2005). The phylogenetic relationships
136 between *N. ceranae* isolates from different host species (*Apis mellifera*, *A. cerana*, *A. florea* and *A. dorsata*)
137 were studied by analysing the sequences of two genes, the ribosomal *SSU* and *PTP1* (Chaimanee *et al.*, 2011).
138 While the former revealed no significant differences between isolates, the latter identified three separate
139 clades, one corresponding to the isolates infecting *A. mellifera* and *A. cerana*, and the other two
140 to *N. ceranae* isolates from *A. florea* and *A. dorsata*. Again, these results should be interpreted with caution, as
141 the lack of cloning could give rise to misleading conclusions (see above). A second study based on a different
142 polar tube protein, *PTP3* (Hatjina *et al.*, 2011), demonstrated that direct sequencing of PCR products may
143 overlook numerous genetic variants, highlighting a significant drawback of genotyping. Surprisingly, the
144 authors found that sequence heterogeneity within a sample was not restricted to rDNA and identified five
145 distinct *PTP3* sequences in five different clones obtained from a single isolate. The basis for this high degree of
146 heterogeneity remains unclear, although it may be possible that multiple copies of the gene exist in a nucleus,
147 that heterozygosis of the two nuclei of a spore occurs or that there is co-infection with several strains.
148 Moreover, the association of specific haplotypes with different levels of host damage remains poorly
149 understood (Tay *et al.*, 2005; Williams *et al.*, 2008). However, it should be noted that virulence is a
150 consequence of the trade-off between different components of parasite fitness in which both parasite and
151 host play essential roles (reviewed by Frank, 1996 and Frank and Schmid-Hempel, 2008). These host–parasite
152 interactions may explain the high levels of polymorphism detected both in the
153 ribosomal *SSU* (Sagastume *et al.*, 2010) and the *PTP3* (Hatjina *et al.*, 2011) genes of *N. ceranae*, although
154 further research is necessary to discern the implications of different haplotypes on virulence, distribution and
155 resistance to fungicides or host defences.

156 Variations in host susceptibility and pathological effects at individual level

157 The host is a key component of the epidemiological triad in any disease. Accordingly, specific differences
158 between lineages have been proposed to underlie the divergent pathological effects of *N. ceranae* in different
159 laboratories or countries. Indeed, a review of the literature available reveals significant differences in the
160 survival and mortality of infected bees between studies.

161 In laboratory experiments, factors including the age of the bees, and the origin dose and purification method of
162 the infective spores, can have a significant impact on the survival of infected bees. For example, the risk of
163 many infectious diseases varies widely over the animals lifespan due to the physiological changes associated
164 with age. Comparable results have been reported when young bees (bred in incubators) are used
165 (Higes *et al.*, 2007; Martín-Hernández *et al.*, 2009; 2011; Alaux *et al.*, 2010; Vidau *et al.*, 2011). In these
166 conditions, mortality is greater in *N. ceranae*-infected versus uninfected bees, and a similar trend is observed
167 when young bees are tested (Higes *et al.*, 2007; Alaux *et al.*, 2010; Martín-Hernández *et al.*, 2011;
168 Aufauvre *et al.*, 2012; Dussaubat *et al.*, 2012), and when worker honeybees from the brood nest are infected
169 (Paxton *et al.*, 2007), with decreased survival in infected versus uninfected bees. However, very low mortality
170 was observed when adult worker bees of undetermined age (average 15 days old) were collected from combs
171 and experimentally infected with *N. ceranae* (Forsgren and Fries, 2010).

172 A second factor affecting the outcome of infection is the source and storage conditions of spore inoculum. The
173 effect of temperature (frozen, refrigerated or fresh) on spore viability and previous handling (if the spores were
174 purified or not and the method used) may explain some conflicting findings regarding infectivity and bee
175 mortality. Differences in thermal plasticity have been demonstrated
176 between *N. apis* and *N. ceranae* (Fenoy *et al.*, 2009; Gisder *et al.*, 2010; reviewed in Martín-
177 Hernández *et al.*, 2009; Fries, 2010) and prior thermal shock may be misinterpreted as variability in virulence
178 or infectivity between strains. Similarly, the spore dose used may directly influence survival of bees.

179 These important methodological differences must be considered when comparing different studies. For
180 example, mortality at 7 days post infection ranged from 11.1% to 93.1% when Percoll-purified spores
181 maintained at room temperature were used to infect newborn honey bees, given individual doses of 10^3 -
182 10^5 spores per bee and maintained at 33°C after infection (Martín-Hernández *et al.*, 2011). In these conditions,
183 the mortality of infected bees was always greater than that observed in uninfected controls. Conversely, in
184 another study fresh spores (no data regarding purification or storage temperature are provided) were used to
185 infect adult worker bees collected from a colony (~ 15 days old) with doses of 10^1 - 10^4 spores per bee, and that
186 were maintained at 30°C post-infection (Forsgren and Fries, 2010). Despite these differences, and even though
187 exhaustive detail on bee mortality was not provided in the latter study, increased mortality (23%) was observed
188 in one cage of bees infected with *N. ceranae*, consistent with the findings of Martín-Hernández and colleagues
189 (2011) with a comparable spore dose per bee. However, the conclusions of both experiments obviously differ
190 and they cannot be compared due to significant methodological differences.

191 The aforementioned discrepancies between studies underscore the need for standardized protocols to
192 compare the effects of *Nosema* infection on honeybee survival rates, in which the following parameters are
193 controlled: spore source, spore storage conditions, spore purification process, spore viability and infectivity,
194 bee incubation temperature, the age of bees at infection, the source of the bees used (colony or laboratory), or
195 even nutritional factors or genetical differences yet to verify. Furthermore, differences in experimental

196 conditions should be highlighted to avoid methodological artefacts that could bias the results and
197 conclusions.

198 In addition to the effects on honeybee mortality, several studies have investigated other aspects of
199 experimental infection with *N. ceranae* in the laboratory, including the effects on hormone and pheromone
200 production (Dussaubat *et al.*, 2010; Alaux *et al.*, 2011; Ares *et al.*, 2012), immune suppression
201 (Antúnez *et al.*, 2009; Chaimanee *et al.*, 2012), energetic stress (Mayack and Naug, 2009; Martín-
202 Hernández *et al.*, 2011), behaviour (Naug and Gibbs, 2009; Campbell *et al.*, 2010), anatomopathological
203 lesions (Higes *et al.*, 2007; 2009b; Paxton *et al.*, 2007; Dussaubat *et al.*, 2012), carbohydrate and aminoacid
204 levels in hemolymph (Mayack and Naug, 2010; Aliferis *et al.*, 2012), tissue degeneration and cell renewal
205 (Dussaubat *et al.*, 2012), as well as its synergy with other agents (Alaux *et al.*, 2010; Vidau *et al.*, 2011;
206 Aufauvre *et al.*, 2012). These studies clearly demonstrate that *N. ceranae* exerts pathological effects
207 on *A. mellifera* similar to those seen in *A. florea* (Suwannapong *et al.*, 2010).

208 In both experimentally and naturally infected bees (*A. mellifera*), *N. ceranae* infection significant alters bee
209 behaviour and the physiology of the infected tissue (ventriculi). In both cases, similar anatomopathological
210 alterations have been reported (Higes *et al.*, 2007; 2009b; Chen *et al.*, 2009a; García-Palencia *et al.*, 2010),
211 including degeneration of the epithelial ventricular cells, the presence of vacuoles in the cytoplasm,
212 disruption of the cellular membranes and a reduced size of the cell nucleus.

213 Based on PCR detection of the parasite, it has been suggested that *N. ceranae* can parasitize structures other
214 than the epithelial cells of the ventriculi in worker bees, such as the Malpighian tubules, hypopharyngeal and
215 salivary glands (Chen *et al.*, 2009a; Gisder *et al.*, 2010; Copley and Jabaji, 2012), head, thorax, ovaries,
216 spermatheca and eggs (Traver and Fell, 2012). However, these results have not been confirmed by
217 histopathological studies and nor have different developmental stages of *Nosema* been observed in cell types
218 other in than the epithelial cells of the ventriculum (Higes *et al.*, 2007; García-Palencia *et al.*, 2010).

219 The numerous negative effects of *N. ceranae* infection of individual honeybees are reflected by further effects
220 at the colony level, directly affecting colony homeostasis. A mathematical model
221 of *Nosema* and *Varroa* infections has been generated and demonstrates how forager death rate influences
222 colony population, suggesting that chronically high forager death rates result in rapid population decline and
223 consequent colony failure (Khoury *et al.*, 2011). Some recent epidemiological studies do not support this
224 model (Fernández *et al.*, 2012; Dainat *et al.*, 2012a,b), although the methodology used in those studies do not
225 let assess adequately the effect of the parasite at the individual and the colony level.

226 All the methodological differences here revised make difficult to establish if the differences in mortality are
227 due to the methodology or to the different susceptibility of the host subspecies. Since recently a Danish strain
228 of bees (drones) get after selective breeding has been described to be more tolerant to *N. ceranae* infections
229 (Huang *et al.*, 2012) more research should be performed with different *A. mellifera* subspecies using
230 standardized methods.

231 Does *Nosema ceranae* present different epidemiological patterns?

232 Environmental conditions also strongly influence many parasitic relationships and, regardless of the effects of
233 altitude, flora and colony management, in warm countries like Spain the influence of temperature on the
234 consequences of *N. ceranae* has been observed. This factor may contribute to the divergent effects

235 of *N. ceranae* on infected colonies around the world and indeed, a different pattern of climatic preferences
236 has been recently described for the two *Nosema* species that infect honeybees (Martín-
237 Hernández *et al.*, 2012). While both species were widely disseminated within the study area, *N. ceranae* was
238 the most prevalent microsporidia found in *A. mellifera* in hotter regions (Mediterranean regions),
239 while *N. apis* was more prevalent in milder regions. Since *N. ceranae* infection appears to be more common in
240 warmer climates and in specific geographical areas, this should be considered when importing bees from
241 such areas (Fries, 2010), when engaging in professional apiculture in warmer countries (e.g. Spain, Greece,
242 Italy), and when evaluating the impact of *Nosema* infection in warm climates.

243 Environmental effects have also been implicated in the interspecies competition
244 between *N. ceranae* and *N. apis*. *Nosema ceranae* is currently the most prevalent microsporidium and
245 frequently, it is the only species detected in bees (Klee *et al.*, 2007; Chen *et al.*, 2008; Chen and Huang, 2010;
246 Yoshiyama and Kimura, 2011; Martínez *et al.*, 2012). However, this tendency was not observed in regions of
247 Germany or the UK (Budge *et al.*, 2010; Gisder *et al.*, 2010) where *N. apis* remains more prevalent.
248 Furthermore, a recent analysis of the prevalence of *Nosema* spp. at different levels (individual, colony, apiary,
249 country, bee castes) revealed that no replacement was observed (Martín-Hernández *et al.*, 2012).
250 Although *N. ceranae* was the dominant species throughout the year, the prevalence of *N. apis* (much lower)
251 followed a classical epidemiological pattern (peaking in spring and autumn), similar to that described
252 historically (Gómez Pajuelo and Fernández Arroyo, 1979; Orantes Bermejo and García-Fernández, 1997).
253 Similar results have been observed too in the USA (Runckel *et al.*, 2011; Dr R. Cramer, pers. comm.).

254 Most classical studies described typical patterns of prevalence in temperate climates, with a large peak in
255 spring when more colonies have detectable levels of infection (Borchert, 1928 reviewed in Bailey, 1955;
256 Fries, 2010). Importantly, when these studies were performed *N. apis* was considered the only aetiological
257 agent of nosemosis. More recently, a lack of seasonality has been reported in tropical and subtropical
258 conditions (Fries and Raina, 2003; reviewed in Fries, 2010), while *N. ceranae* infection has always been
259 detected throughout the year at different latitudes (Martín-Hernández *et al.*, 2007; 2012; Calderón *et al.*, 2008;
260 Higes *et al.*, 2008; Hedtke *et al.*, 2011; Runckel *et al.*, 2011; Stevanovic *et al.*, 2011; Traver and Fell, 2011;
261 Whitaker *et al.*, 2011; Medici *et al.*, 2012; Smart and Sheppard, 2012; Botías *et al.*, 2012a,b;
262 Dainat *et al.*, 2012a).

263 In any discussion of environmental effects, seasonality must be defined. In early studies, this term only
264 described the detection of the agent, or the observation of clinical signs at a particular time point. However,
265 with the development of new scientific methods, seasonality is now measured on the basis of prevalence
266 (Fries, 2010), the percentage of infected bees (Higes *et al.*, 2008), the mean spore count (Higes *et al.*, 2008,
267 Traver *et al.*, 2011), the Ct value and the average copy numbers (Traver and Fell, 2012). The use of one or other
268 parameter has a direct impact on the epidemiological pattern. For instance, although spore count is not a
269 reliable parameter of infection (Meana *et al.*, 2010), comparing colony infection using this parameter reveals a
270 higher level in spring (April–June: Gisder *et al.*, 2010; Traver and Fell, 2011; Traver *et al.*, 2012) or in autumn–
271 winter (Higes *et al.*, 2008).

272 Finally, the fact is that *N. ceranae* is highly prevalent in warmer areas and its presence in the colony is very
273 high. Under those conditions there are many bees infected that can be directly related to the clinical signs
274 observed under field conditions.

275 Clinical signs of *N. ceranae* infection in honeybee colonies

276 Probably the most controversial aspect of *N. ceranae* infection in beekeeping is its ability to depopulate or kill
277 a colony. After *N. ceranae* parasitization of honeybees was first detected and linked with colony collapse in
278 Spain (Higes *et al.*, 2006; Martín-Hernández *et al.*, 2007), other authors ruled out its role in colony loss (Cox-
279 Foster *et al.*, 2007; Klee *et al.*, 2007). At this time, the little data available on the virulence of *N. ceranae* at the
280 colony level were contradictory, probably due to a failure to properly identify the clinical signs of disease, the
281 parameter with which to evaluate the impact of the illness and a poor understanding of the subclinical effects
282 of parasitism. Moreover, at the time, the only common feature of colony collapse described all over the world
283 was death.

284 Traditionally Koch's postulates have been used as criteria to determine whether a given microorganism causes
285 a specific disease. Those postulates were initially developed for bacteria and despite their importance in
286 microbiology, they have severe limitations particularly when applied to diseases caused by non-bacterial
287 microorganisms. For example, for some microorganisms that cannot be grown in pure culture in the
288 laboratory, including bee microsporidia, they can be used to infect the host, mimicking the disease. Additional
289 limitations arise in cases where the clinical signs of an infection have not been accurately described (or widely
290 accepted), as is the case of nosemosis type C caused by *N. ceranae* infection.

291 Taking these limitations into account, Koch's postulates were demonstrated for honeybee colonies infected
292 with *N. ceranae* (Higes *et al.*, 2008), as previously confirmed in individual bees (see above). *Nosema*
293 *ceranae* was extracted from an affected colony and identified by PCR, and it was then transmitted to healthy
294 colonies where it induced disease and colony collapse. Finally, the infective agent was isolated from these
295 newly infected colonies. These findings were subsequently confirmed in later studies (Botías *et al.*, 2010;
296 2012a) and among other pathogens, colony loss has been linked with the presence of *N. ceranae* in several
297 reports (Higes *et al.*, 2005; 2006; 2008; 2009a; Borneck *et al.*, 2010; Hatjina *et al.*, 2011; Nabian *et al.*, 2011).
298 However, studies conducted in colder areas have revealed contradictory findings (Gisder *et al.*, 2010;
299 Hedtke *et al.*, 2011; Stevanovic *et al.*, 2011; Dainat *et al.*, 2012a,b). Thus, it is of great interest to determine
300 whether these differential effects results are due to distinct behaviours of *N. ceranae* at different latitudes, or
301 basic criteria are not the same such as the identification of clinical/subclinical signs of disease between
302 researchers. In some works definition of colony loss or collapsed colonies are the only description of a disease
303 that seems not to present any other clinical sign. An expert is sometimes needed to detect signs as lower bee
304 population, lower honey production, unexpected brood in cold months or younger bees starting to forage. Due
305 to the fact that bees are social insects, a biological point of view must be properly differentiate from a
306 veterinarian one, each one complementing the other.

307 **A biological perspective**

308 Honeybee colonies are social systems whose performance depends on the equilibrium that exists between
309 the members of the colony. Accordingly, any effects at the individual level due to *N. ceranae* infection will
310 disturb colony homeostasis. The colony population depends largely on the lifespan of the worker bees
311 (Woyke, 1984; Khoury *et al.*, 2011), which may be severely affected by *N. ceranae* infection (Higes *et al.*, 2007;
312 Paxton *et al.*, 2007; Martín-Hernández *et al.*, 2011). These findings demonstrate that *N. ceranae* can actively
313 reduce the adult bee population (Higes *et al.*, 2008; Botías *et al.*, 2010; 2012a; Soroker *et al.*, 2011;
314 Eischen *et al.*, 2012).

315 A direct consequence of the high mortality rate of foragers that is provoked by *Nosema* infection
316 (Higes *et al.*, 2008; 2010), is that younger bees begin to forage earlier to compensate for the loss of available
317 foragers (Huang and Robinson, 1996; Amdam and Omholt, 2003), thereby modifying the entire work profile of
318 the colony (Wang and Moeller, 1970). However, this compensatory mechanism shortens the overall lifespan of
319 adult bees (Neukirch, 1982; Schmid-Hempel and Wolf, 1988; Wolf and Schmid-Hempel, 1989), and their
320 efficacy and resilience as foragers (Oskey, 2007), as well as reducing the time each bee dedicates to colony
321 growth and brood production. Furthermore, internal colony activities such as hygiene and brood caring may be
322 negatively affected due to the decreased availability of nurse bees that attend to the brood, in turn increasing
323 the risk of developing brood diseases such as chalkbrood (Hedtke *et al.*, 2011). When the colony reaches the
324 point at which it cannot sustain brood production at a sufficient rate to replace the adult bee losses, the extent
325 of colony decline accelerates rapidly, resulting in depopulation (Khoury *et al.*, 2011), which represents the only
326 clear sign of infection described for *Nosema ceranae* (Higes *et al.*, 2008; 2011; Botías *et al.*, 2010; 2012a;
327 Eischen *et al.*, 2012).

328 The accelerated behavioural development observed in *Nosema*-infected bees has been associated with
329 increased titres of juvenile hormone (JH: Lin *et al.*, 2009; reviewed in Higes *et al.*, 2010; Ares *et al.*, 2012),
330 inhibition of vitellogenin (Vg) gene expression (Antúnez *et al.*, 2009) and increased levels of the pheromone
331 ethyl oleate (EO: Dussaubat *et al.*, 2010). These factors are implicated in regulating the division of labour
332 among worker bees, as well as maturation and the nurse–forager transition. This manipulation of host
333 endocrinology in infected insects has previously been described as an adaptive mechanism that serves to
334 increase the reproductive fitness of the parasite (prolonging the host larval state to maximize spore yield:
335 Down *et al.*, 2008).

336 *Nosema ceranae* also significantly alters the feeding behaviour of infected bees, increasing their
337 responsiveness to sucrose and decreasing food sharing between bees (Naug and Gibbs, 2009). In addition,
338 this microsporidium can lower the haemolymph sugar level of individual foragers and uncouple their energetic
339 state from that of the colony, to which it is normally closely related (Mayack and Naug, 2010). In turn, this
340 altered energetic state can decrease the flying ability of foragers by about two-thirds when compared with
341 uninfected foragers, as confirmed by the impaired orientation skills in *Nosema*-infected bees and a lower rate
342 of infected bees among the returning versus departing foragers (Kralj and Fuchs, 2010). This observation
343 suggests that infected forager bees die while foraging, as described previously (Higes *et al.*, 2008). Accordingly,
344 it is unusual to find dead or dying bees in the vicinity of the hive in cases of nosemosis type C
345 (Higes *et al.*, 2008; 2009a; 2010; Borneck *et al.*, 2010).

346 The preference for higher temperatures exhibited by *N. ceranae*-infected bees (Campbell *et al.*, 2010) may be
347 due to the pathological stress imposed on the host by the infection. However, this preference also appears to
348 benefit the pathogen, as the reproductive potential of *N. ceranae* increases at higher temperatures (Martín-
349 Hernández *et al.*, 2009). Energetic stress and a concurrent increase in appetite are the primary effects
350 of *N. ceranae* infection in honeybees (Mayack and Naug, 2009). This increased energetic stress may explain
351 some of the changes observed in host behaviour due to starvation, lack of thermoregulatory capacity or
352 alterations in the rates of trophallaxis, which may enhance disease transmission and increase the risk of death
353 (Martín-Hernández *et al.*, 2011). Indeed, these changes in the hive conditions may also be implicated in
354 outbreaks of stress-related diseases such as chalkbrood (Hedtke *et al.*, 2011) or even in the loss of efficacy of
355 contact-dependent treatments to control the parasite *Varroa destructor* (Botías *et al.*, 2011).

356 A colony infected with *Nosema* constantly loses old bees, which are supplemented by younger bees. The
357 percentage of younger bees in the colony population can explain the large differences in parasite burden (as
358 either percentage of infected bees or parasite burden) observed at the moment of death. Colonies that die in
359 winter generally contain few or no newborns. Accordingly, the surviving interior bees are strongly infected and
360 can even transmit the infection to the queen (Higes *et al.*, 2008; 2009b). If the colony collapses in early spring,
361 the increasing numbers of newborn bees will reduce the percentage of infected interior bees and the parasitic
362 load, such that the intensity of infection will be lower than that seen in winter (Higes *et al.*, 2008). This scenario
363 differs to that which occurs when colonies collapse due to *Varroa destructor* infection
364 (Rosenkranz *et al.*, 2010). In this case, the bees that remain at the time of the collapse exhibit a high infestation
365 rate due to exponential multiplication of mites in the previous months. The unawareness of these factors
366 could explain discrepancies found in some works (Cox-Foster *et al.*, 2007; Dainat *et al.*, 2012a,b;
367 Fernández *et al.*, 2012).

368 In addition to the effects of infection on colony dynamics, several additional factors may increase the severity
369 of *N. ceranae* infection in field conditions, including exposure to sublethal doses of insecticides
370 (Wu *et al.*, 2012), which can increase mortality and colony susceptibility to pathogens and promote the
371 interaction of certain viruses (Bromenshenk *et al.*, 2010; Bacandritsos *et al.*, 2010). A recent study reported a
372 negative correlation between deformed wing virus (DWV) and *N. ceranae* (Costa *et al.*, 2011), which may result
373 from competition for host cells or specific cell functions in the honeybee midgut: *N. ceranae* induces lesions
374 and degeneration of the epithelial cells of this tissue (Higes *et al.*, 2007), and the digestive tract appears to be
375 critical for DWV pathogenesis (Boncristiani *et al.*, 2009).

376 **A veterinary perspective**

377 In veterinary medicine, a clinical sign is an objective indication of a specific medical event or characteristic
378 that can be detected by a veterinarian during an examination or by a clinical scientist by means of *in vivo* or *in*
379 *vitro* analysis of the subject of interest. Because each group member is differently affected by one or more of
380 the factors of the epidemiologic triad, a disease in a group (apiary) is often manifested as a spectrum ranging
381 from unapparent to subclinical to clinical to fatal. In this context, clinical signs are indications of disease that
382 can be detected during a normal clinical examination, while subclinical signs are indications of disease that
383 cannot be detected without performing a specific test. Decreased productivity is one of the most common
384 subclinical signs in farming animals.

385 Many analyses of *N. ceranae* infection measure only colony losses in a short time period (as example
386 Williams *et al.*, 2010; Fernández *et al.*, 2012). However, independent of their role as pollinators, honeybees are
387 farm animals that produce food and non-food products of human interest, although honeybee diseases are
388 not usually discussed in this context. Indeed, the effects of microsporidia infection on hive products remain
389 largely unknown. Several factors may affect honey production by honeybee colonies, including climatic
390 conditions (Kauffeld *et al.*, 1976; Giray *et al.*, 2007; vanEngelsdorp and Meixner, 2010), the availability of an
391 adequate foraging area (Naug, 2009), and colony strength (i.e. brood production, adult bee population, worker
392 bee lifespan and worker bee productivity: Woyke, 1984; Szabo and Lefkovitch, 1989; Eckert *et al.*, 1994).
393 Furthermore, honeybee parasites and pathogens have for long been reported to negatively influence colony
394 productivity (Kauffeld *et al.*, 1972; Fries, 1988; Anderson and Giaccon, 1992; Murilhas, 2002).

395 As negative effects of *N. apis* infection on colony productivity have been reported previously (Farrar, 1947;
396 Moeller, 1962; Kauffeld *et al.*, 1972; Fries *et al.*, 1984), similar effects were assumed for *N. ceranae*, given its
397 rapid spread and high prevalence (reviewed by Fries, 2010 and Higes *et al.*, 2010). Indeed, honey production
398 has been directly correlated with the level of colony infection (Botías *et al.*, 2010; 2012a). A negative
399 correlation between *N. ceranae* infection rates (percentage of infected forager bees per colony) and colony
400 honey production (determined by weighing the amount of honey produced per colony) was described in field
401 studies of experimental colonies in Spain (Botías *et al.*, 2010; 2012a). Nevertheless, a recent publication from
402 Spain (Fernández *et al.*, 2012) suggested that *N. ceranae* infected honey bee colonies remained alive with
403 normal production during the referenced study. Surprisingly the honey and pollen production were not
404 recorded during the assay, and other clinical or subclinical signs were not taken into account or measured. For
405 this reason this statement has to be evaluated cautiously. However, additional data collected in different
406 climates with different beekeeping management techniques are required to corroborate these findings. In a
407 Canadian study, honey and pollen cells were visually evaluated as indicators of colony strength to compare
408 untreated and fumagillin-treated colonies (Williams *et al.*, 2010). No correlation was established between the
409 presence of *N. ceranae* and colony strength or winter mortality, although not all fumagillin-treated and
410 untreated groups studied exhibited different levels of infection.

411 The probability of acquiring an infectious disease increases with age, and novel diseases can be readily picked
412 up by foraging bees (Schmid-Hempel, 1994). Accordingly, several studies have reported that forager bees are
413 more likely to be infected with *Nosema* than house bees (L'Arrivée, 1963; Taber and Lee, 1973; Pickard and EL-
414 Shemy, 1989; Higes *et al.*, 2008; Meana *et al.*, 2010; Botías *et al.*, 2012a; Martín-Hernández *et al.*, 2012; Smart
415 and Sheppard, 2012). By contrast, a recent study reported no significant differences in the extent of infection
416 between in-hive and forager bees (Traver *et al.*, 2012), although both parameters, the average DNA copy
417 number and average spore count of *N. ceranae*, tended to be higher in the forager bee samples.

418 Another aspect of *N. ceranae* infection that is rarely assessed is the influence of beekeeping practices on
419 disease evolution at the colony level. A recent study demonstrated the central role of the queen in the
420 evolution of *N. ceranae* infection of honeybee colonies (Botías *et al.*, 2012a). Removal of the queen and
421 subsequent replacement with a younger queen decreased the proportion of *Nosema* infected forager and
422 house bees, maintaining the overall infection rate at a level compatible with colony viability. This effect should
423 be taken into account when studying the evolution of *Nosema* disease in different geographical areas where
424 queens are frequently replaced (either naturally or by the beekeeper). Possible repercussions of different
425 beekeeping practices such as prophylactic measures should also be considered, as their effects
426 on *N. ceranae* have not been established, and handling techniques used in Northern Europe
427 (Hedtke *et al.*, 2011) differ widely from those of Mediterranean areas (Higes *et al.*, 2008; 2009a; 2010;
428 Bacandritsos *et al.*, 2010; Hatjina *et al.*, 2011).

429 In summary, the data currently available indicate that *N. ceranae* is an important pathogen of honeybee
430 colonies (Fig. 2). This microsporidian induces an illness now known as nosemosis type C (Higes *et al.*, 2010),
431 which presents a variety of manifestations due to several factors, some of which are understood and others
432 that remain to be identified. Indeed, many of the clinical signs produced by this disease have received little
433 attention, with colony collapse generally taken as the main disease indicator by both researchers and
434 beekeepers.

435 The disease produced by *N. ceranae* infection cannot be considered a Spanish regional problem as previously
436 suggested, but rather a global one, as indicated by the wide prevalence of this parasite in multiple hosts. Not
437 only does this type of nosemosis affect honeybees at both the individual and colony levels, but it also has
438 significant effects on the production of honeybee products. Accordingly, in addition to colony collapse, it is
439 essential to continue studying the many effects of *N. ceranae* infection in bee colonies in different
440 geographical regions, in order to provide beekeepers with appropriate control strategies. This is particularly
441 necessary in temperate zones, such as Mediterranean countries, where *N. ceranae* is more prevalent and
442 more damaging. Moreover, this region is home to a large number of professional beekeepers and it produces
443 high yields of honey and pollen, highlighting the importance of minimizing the economic toll
444 of *N. ceranae* infection. For this reason we cannot simply bury our head in the sand but for the sake of these
445 professional beekeepers, we must search for a practical solution to this problem.

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805 **Figure 1.** Mature spore of *Nosema ceranae* (electron microscopy).

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809 **Figure 2.** A honey bee colony collapsed by *Nosema ceranae*.

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